

The Homeric Hymn to Hermes

also known as "Homeric Hymn 4"

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Entry tags: Hymn, Ancient Mediterranean, Religious Group, Text, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Ancient Greek text, Language, Greek Cult, Greek Religions, Graeco-Phrygian, Greek

The Homeric Hymn to Hermes (Homeric Hymn 4) is the longest of the 33 surviving ancient Greek hymns traditionally attributed to Homer, the semi-legendary composer of the Iliad and Odyssey. Though the Hymn to Hermes, like the other Homeric Hymns, has important stylistic, narrative, and thematic similarities to the Iliad and Odyssey, modern scholars do not believe that these poems were composed by the composer or composers of the Iliad and Odyssey. The Homeric Hymn to Hermes narrates the first three days of the life of Hermes, the Greek god associated with messengers, travel, and thieves. In the hymn, the young Hermes invents the lyre, steals the cattle of his brother Apollo, and finally receives a "crash course" in divination. Music and song are important themes throughout, and humor is used very prominently. On the basis of the language and content of the poem, scholars have often argued for a date of composition in the second half of the sixth century BCE.

Date Range: 550 BCE - 500 BCE

Region: Classical Greece

Region tags: Europe, Western Europe

Roughly the area encompassing the core of Classical Greek culture.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Thomas, Oliver. The Homeric Hymn to Hermes (Cambridge Classical Texts and Commentaries 62). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020.
- Source 2: Vergados, Athanassios. A Commentary on the Homeric Hymn to Hermes. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2012.
- Source 3: Brown, Norman. Hermes the Thief. Madison: University of Wisconsin Press, 1947

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0137%3Ahymn%3D4>

– Source 1 Description: Original text and translation of the Homeric Hymn to Hermes

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0137%3Ahymn%3D4>

– Source 1 Description: Original text and translation of the Homeric Hymn to Hermes

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: Like the Homeric epics and the other Homeric Hymns, the Homeric Hymn to Hermes was performed, transmitted, and to some extent composed orally. The poem thus reflects the oral framework and oral poetic techniques (such of formulaic phraseology, traditional structures, etc.) of Archaic Greek literature. But the Hymn to Hermes was also composed at a time when literacy was becoming increasingly widespread in Greece, and the poet himself raises the subject of composition and performance when he refers to Hermes' first song at line 55 as ἐξ αὐτοσχεδίου, that is, "off-hand" or "improvised," perhaps suggesting a contrast between improvisatory (oral) composition techniques and written (literate) composition.

Reference: Vergados, Athanassios. The "homeric Hymn to Hermes". DE GRUYTER, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110259704.p.73-75>

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no way of knowing whether the production of the text was officially funded. Sarah Iles Johnston has argued that the hymn was composed for a religious festival such as the Hermaia, but she has not suggested any specific venue for the original performance. Some of the places where scholars have attempted to place the composition of the hymn include Attica, Ionia, Euboea, Boeotia, and Delphi.

Reference: Vergados, Athanassios. The "homerich Hymn to Hermes". DE GRUYTER, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110259704>. p.148-53

Reference: Johnston, Sarah Iles. "Myth, Festival, and Poet: The "homerich Hymn to Hermes" and Its Performative Context" 97, no. 2 (April 2002). <https://doi.org/10.1086/449575>.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymn to Hermes employs archaic language resembling the language of Homer and Hesiod. But there are also enough linguistic innovations that many scholars have argued for a later date of composition.

Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars have argued for the presence of linguistic forms from certain dialects (e.g., Atticisms), but these are far from definitively established.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Homeric Hymns were composed for oral performance at public occasions (such as festivals) and/or at large private gatherings at the houses of nobles. The exact size of the audiences typically present at performances of the hymns are unknown. It has been argued that the Homeric Hymn to Hermes would have been performed at festivals to Hermes such as the Hermaia, but this argument is also speculative.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The Homeric Hymns were usually performed as *prooimia*, that is, as sung preludes to longer epic performances. As one of the long Homeric Hymns, the Homeric Hymn to Hermes was probably eventually performed independently, though there is no definite information regarding its performance contexts.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymn to Hermes is known from 23 Medieval manuscripts. For detailed discussions and references to the manuscript tradition in the context of the Homeric Hymn to Apollo, see the apparatus criticus of most modern editions of the Greek text (Càssola's edition especially is highly regarded).

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The long Homeric Hymn to Hermes is traditionally numbered as the fourth Homeric Hymn.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Homeric Hymns were described in antiquity as *prooimia*, that is, poetic preludes performed to introduce longer poetic performances (especially epic performances).

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: The Hymns draws on the vocabulary and phraseology of Greek epic, such as the Homeric epics.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The text lays great emphasis on Hermes' being born on the fourth day of the month, but does not formulate any specifically religious calendar.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Hermes' role as psychopompos, or conveyor of the souls of the dead to the afterlife, is briefly mentioned at the end of the hymn.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Zeus, the father of Hermes, arbitrates a quarrel between Hermes and Apollo in the hymn.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Notes: Though Zeus was sometimes worshiped in a chthonic capacity, the hymn presents him in his more common Olympian (heavenly) capacity.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - No
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: N/A
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - Notes: In the agon between Hermes and Apollo, Zeus easily sees through Hermes' deceit.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: In the text, Hermes' attempt to deceive Apollo and the other gods makes Zeus laugh.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– Yes

↳ Can be hurt?

– Yes

Notes: There are myths that represent Zeus being hurt, such as some versions of the Typhon myth.

↳ Can be tricked?

– Yes

Notes: Zeus is not taken in by Hermes' cunning in the text. There are, however, other myths that represent Zeus being tricked, e.g., the myth of how Prometheus tricked Zeus into accepting the inedible parts of animals for sacrifices.

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– Yes

Notes: There are myths that represent Zeus being imprisoned, such as some versions of the Typhon myth.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

–Specify: N/A

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Gods such as Hermes and Apollo have extensive knowledge of the world, especially through divination (see e.g., the description of the obscure Bee Women at the end of the hymn).

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: One of the many epithets of Hermes given in the hymn is "he who watches at night" (νυκτὸς ὀπωπιητῆρα, line 15)

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Apollo's role as an oracular god is strongly emphasized at the end of the hymn, where Apollo refuses to share his oracular knowledge with Hermes.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: In the text, both Hermes and Apollo speak with an old mortal man.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: Though not present in the text, the Greeks believed that the Pythia, Apollo's priestess at Delphi, delivered oracles communicated to her while in a kind of trance.

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: N/A

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: Notably, the text represents Apollo becoming very angry at Hermes when he steals his cattle.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: In a remarkable passage, the text represents Hermes feeling a great longing (ἡράσσατο, line 130) for the cattle he sacrificed, even though as a god he cannot eat human food.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: N/A

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: The hymn contains an agon scene in which Zeus, as the ruler of the pantheon, arbitrates between his sons Apollo and Hermes.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Several gods have important manifestations or epiphanies in the text, e.g., the appearance of Hermes and later Apollo to the old man. Much is made of the contrast between Hermes' infantile appearance and his maturity.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Hermes' use of his infantile appearance to disguise his true nature can be understood as hiding his aspect from others, especially Apollo.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text alludes to divination practices, especially in Apollo's description of the Bee Women at the end of the hymn, but it does not specifically guide divination practices.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: There are references in the text to the ability of the gods to punish, but no punishments are actually meted out in the text.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: There are references in the text to the ability of the gods to reward, but no rewards are actually bestowed in the text.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: Hermes' role as psychopompos, or conveyor of the souls of the dead to the afterlife, is mentioned in the text; however, there is no eschatology present.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

Notes: Some episodes described in the text, especially the means Hermes uses to escape the clutches of his brother Apollo, were clearly intended to be comical.

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymns draw on epic language and phraseology and were probably performed as preludes to epic performances.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions animal sacrifices and describes Hermes' sacrifice of cattle.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

Notes: The Greek world was split up into numerous city-states (or poleis) at the time that the Homeric Hymns were composed. It is uncertain in which city-state the Homeric Hymn to Hermes originated, however.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymns seem to have been taught and to have been a subject of scholarly study in antiquity. They are still taught at universities today.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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General References

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Entry/Answer References

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